

Assessment of Occupational Aspirations of Students with Disabilities in Integrated Secondary Schools in Southwest, Nigeria

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Abstract

This study assessed occupational aspirations of students with disabilities in integrated secondary schools in Southwest, Nigeria. The descriptive research design of the survey type was used in this study. The population consisted of all 1,106 students with disabilities in integrated public secondary schools in Southwest, Nigeria. The sample for this study consisted of 349 students with disabilities from 12 integrated public secondary schools in Southwest, Nigeria. The sample was selected via multi stage sampling procedure. An instrument tagged "Occupational Aspiration Questionnaire (OAQ)" was used to collect relevant data for the study from the respondents. The validity of the instrument was ensured through face, content and construct validity. Convergent construct validity between MOPS (standardized instrument) and OAQ yielded $r = 0.859$. The data collected from the questionnaire were analyzed using descriptive and inferential statistics. The findings of the study revealed that students with disabilities have highest preference for business based occupation, closely followed by art/humanity based occupation and science based occupation while the least preference was technology based occupation. It was also revealed that the occupational aspirations of students with disabilities in integrated secondary schools differ. In addition, occupational aspirations of integrated secondary school students with disabilities do not differ based on their gender and religion. It was recommended among others that the government should create a department that will provide career guidance for students with disabilities.

Keywords: Occupational Aspirations, Disabilities, Integrated Schools,

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Introduction

There shows to be diverse kinds and degrees of disabilities that occur in endowed and talented children, mental retardation, speech impairment, hearing impairment, learning disability, physical impairment to mental and developmental disabilities, not excluding the various kinds of invisible disabilities, some of which are not even visible and identified as disabilities. Notwithstanding all these diversities and, in fact, duly considering the concerns of each of them, certain common factors, definitions and combined understanding would have to be attained for the purposes of analysis and discussion. However, the researcher is interested in students with visible disabilities because of their easy recognition and presence in integrated secondary schools. Students with seen disabilities like visual impairment, physical impairment and hearing impairment can be easily spotted unlike other forms of disabilities.

The integration method is an essential model where both disabled and nondisabled students are taught within the same school. Educational combination, then, offers education focused to include all students, even those with disabilities in the same learning location. This may consist of special needs of children who have emotional and/or behavioural challenges. Teachers may come across a variety of circumstances in the classroom, including those with learning disorders, emotional disabilities, and mental retardation. Exceptional needs students are placed in the usual education classroom and are involved in instructional situations that may have the general education teacher, the special education teacher, the teacher assistant and possibly parental or community volunteers (Wiebe & Kim, 2008).

According to Ahmad (2000), incorporated education is the education of all children and young people with and without disabilities in learning together in ordinary nursery, primary schools, colleges, and universities with suitable network support. In integrated school setting, the gifted/exceptional child is more educationally comfortable to the level that his/her inadequacies brought about by his/her disabilities are decreased. This means that incorporating implies the taking part of persons with disabilities in every academic related endeavour or activities with their non-disabled counter parts. Integrated education is also viewed as an educational strategy that provides opportunity, admittance and enabling atmosphere for all children to be equitably well-informed without isolation or discrimination irrespective of perceived abilities or restrictions.

Research has shown that persons with disabilities are at constraints when it comes to occupational journey and progress in that they are more likely to be without a job or underemployed than colleagues without disabilities and less likely to pursue and achieve postsecondary education or added job training (Ochs & Roessler, 2001). It was evident that students with disabilities have limited chances for occupational progress and these limited opportunities may cause occupational uncertainty which, from every sphere shows to be the grounds why they are less successful than their mates when making the movement from high school into the world of work. They show to have a smaller amount of time to explore and make an effort to occupation-related courses and activities because they may have been deemed needless (Luzzo, 2000); and are notably less able to select occupational goals fitting for their disability and less informed about job opportunities and occupations.

Sex can be seen as a socially constructed sex, be it female or male. On the basis of gender discrimination, disabled boys may be prioritized over girls with disabilities for family expenditure on education, while, in some situations, the rate at which opportunities available for disabled girls and boys vary depending on the cultural, and socio-economic, contexts. In some culture, Girls with disabilities face unfairness with respect to security and safety, thus girls with disabilities are more susceptible to physical and sexual abuse. In addition to

maltreatment at home, it can happen in school or on the way to school (Agran & Wehmeyer, 2014).

Girls seem to be discriminated against from birth, have lower life expectancy and receive less care, especially if they are disabled. They may be considered an extra stress or cause of despair which may influence their occupational aspiration or decision. It was observed that female students with disabilities are faced with higher prejudice. Whereas the occupation journey of the non-disabled female students appears to be hindered by their gender. Being a male or female could therefore be expected to affect the job/career aspirations of students with disabilities differently.

This study therefore assessed occupational aspirations of students with disabilities in integrated secondary schools in Southwest, Nigeria. The study specifically examined:

- i. the occupational aspirations of students with disabilities in secondary schools;
- ii. difference in the occupational aspirations of students with disabilities in integrated secondary schools;
- iii. the sex difference in occupational aspirations of integrated secondary school students with disabilities; and
- iv. the difference in occupational aspirations of integrated secondary school students with disabilities based on their religion.

Research Question

This research question was raised to guide the study:

1. What are the occupational aspirations of students with disabilities in secondary schools in South-west, Nigeria?

Research Hypotheses

The following null hypotheses were formulated for this study:

1. There is no significant difference in the occupational aspirations of students with disabilities in integrated secondary schools.
2. There is no significant sex difference in occupational aspirations of integrated secondary school students with disabilities.
3. Religion will not significantly differentiate in the occupational aspirations of integrated secondary school students with disabilities.

Methodology

The descriptive research design of the survey type was used in this study. The population consisted of all 1,106 students with disabilities in integrated public secondary schools in Southwest, Nigeria. The states were Lagos, Ogun, Oyo, Osun, Ondo and Ekiti. In Lagos state, there were 297 students with disabilities, in Ogun state, 184; in Oyo state, 168; in Osun state, 172; in Ondo state, 146; and in Ekiti state, 139 (**Source:** State Ministries of Education, 2019).

The sample for this study consisted of 349 students with disabilities from 12 integrated public secondary schools in Southwest, Nigeria. The sample was selected via multi stage sampling procedure. In stage one, four states were selected from the six states in Southwest, Nigeria through simple random sampling technique. The second stage involved the selection of three Local Government Areas from each of the four States through purposive sampling technique because the local government area where an integrated secondary school is located was selected. In stage three, one integrated public secondary school was selected from each of the Local Government Areas earlier selected through purposive sampling technique. The reason for using purposive in selecting the schools was because the three types of disabilities were considered in the study. In stage four, thirty students with disabilities were selected from each of the integrated public secondary schools using

purposive random sampling technique. The reason for using purposive technique in selecting students with disabilities was to ensure that those with visual impairment, hearing impairment and physical impairment were equally selected and represented.

An instrument tagged "Occupational Aspiration Questionnaire (OAQ)" was used to collect relevant data for the study from the respondents. OAQ consisted of two sections namely section A and B. *Section A* of the OAQ sought for information on demography about the respondents which included sex, religion among others. *Section B* consisted of 20 items on occupational aspiration of students drawn from science based, art/humanities based, business based and technological based. Adapted four point Likert type rating scale was used for section C as follows: Like Very Much (LVM), Like (L), Dislike (D) and Dislike Very Much (DVM). Like Very Much was scored 4 points, Like was scored 3 points, and Dislike was scored 2 points while Dislike Very Much was scored 1 point. The braille version of the instrument was produced for the visually impaired students.

The validity of the instrument was ensured through face, content and construct validity. The experts took time to check the extent to which the items of the instrument represent the content of the study and suitability of the items being measured. In ensuring the construct validity of Occupational Aspiration Questionnaire (OAQ), a standardized instrument, Motivation for Occupational Preference Scale (MOPS) was compared with OAQ. Convergent Construct Validity between MOPS and OAQ yielded $r = 0.859$. The coefficient value was gotten after analysing the data collected using Pearson's Product Moment Correlation Coefficient. The data compared were gotten from students' response to MOPS and OAQ after it was administered on 30 students outside the sampled area. Based on that, the OAQ is capable of measuring the occupational aspiration of students.

The data collected from the questionnaire were analyzed using descriptive and inferential statistics. The research question was answered using frequency count, mean, standard deviation and chart. The hypotheses were tested using inferential statistics involving one - way Analysis of Variance and t - test at 0.05 level of significance.

Results

Research Question 1: What are the occupational aspirations of students with disabilities in secondary schools in South-west, Nigeria?

In answering this question, data on occupational aspirations were collected from the responses of the respondents to items under Section B of OAQ (item 1 - 20) in the questionnaire. The data were collated and analysed using descriptive statistics such as frequency counts, percentage, mean and standard deviation.

Table 1: Percentage and Mean Scores of occupational aspirations of students with disabilities

S/N	ITEMS	Total Mean	Average Mean	Rank
1	Science Based	9.61	1.92	3 rd
2	Art/Humanity Based	9.89	1.98	2 nd
3	Business Based	11.69	2.34	1 st
4	Technology Based	9.32	1.86	4 th

Figure i: Bar chart showing occupational aspirations of students with disabilities

Table 1 and figure i showed the occupational aspirations of students with disabilities in secondary schools in South-west, Nigeria. The result indicated that the total mean mark of science based occupation is ($\bar{x} = 9.61$), art/humanity based occupation ($\bar{x} = 9.89$), business based occupation ($\bar{x} = 11.69$) and technology based ($\bar{x} = 9.32$). It is deduced from the above that students with disabilities have highest preference for business based occupation, closely followed by art/humanity based occupation and science based occupation while the least preference was technology based occupation.

Testing of Hypotheses

Hypothesis 1: There is no significant difference in the occupational aspirations of students with disabilities in integrated secondary schools.

Table 2: Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) for difference in the occupational aspirations of students with disabilities

Groups	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Between Groups	2598.557	2	1299.278	23.662*	.000
Within Groups	18998.532	346	54.909		
Total	21597.089	348			

* $P < 0.05$

The result presented in table 2 showed that F-cal value of 23.662 was significant at 0.05 level of significance. Hence, the null hypothesis is rejected. This implies that there was significant difference in the occupational aspirations of students with disabilities in integrated secondary schools. In order to investigate the source of the differences observed, Post - hoc analysis (Scheffe) with mean difference was carried out.

Table 3: Scheffe Post – hoc test and mean for observed difference in the occupational aspirations of students with disabilities

Groups	N	Mean	1	2	3
			44.28	38.25	38.87
Visual Impaired (1)	120	44.28			
Hearing Impaired (2)	118	38.25	*		
Physical Impairment (3)	111	38.87	*		

*P < 0.05

In table 3, significant difference was found between the occupational aspirations of hearing impaired students and visually impaired students in integrated secondary schools. Also, a significant difference was found between the occupational aspirations of physical impaired students and visual impaired students in integrated secondary schools. However, significant difference was not found between the occupational aspirations of physical impaired students and hearing impaired students in integrated secondary schools.

Hypothesis 2: There is no significant sex difference in occupational aspirations of integrated secondary school students with disabilities.

Table 4: Sex difference in occupational aspirations

Variations	N	Mean	SD	df	t _{cal}	P
Male	217	40.68	7.89	347	0.488	0.626
Female	132	40.26	7.88			

P > 0.05

Table 4 shows that the t-cal value of 0.488 was not significant because the P value (0.626) > 0.05. This implies that null hypothesis was not rejected. Hence, there was no significant sex difference in occupational aspirations of integrated secondary school students with disabilities.

Hypothesis 3: Religion will not significantly differentiate in the occupational aspirations of integrated secondary school students with disabilities.

Table 5: Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) for difference in the occupational aspirations of students with disabilities

Groups	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Between Groups	45.873	2	22.937	0.368	.692
Within Groups	21551.216	346	62.287		
Total	21597.089	348			

P > 0.05

The result presented in table 5 showed that F-cal value of 0.368 is not significant at 0.05 level of significance because p-value of 0.692 > 0.05. Hence, the null hypothesis is not rejected. This implies that religion will not significantly differentiate in the occupational aspirations of integrated secondary school students with disabilities.

Discussion

The study revealed that students with disabilities have highest preference for business based occupation, closely followed by art/humanity based occupation and science based occupation while the least preference was technology based occupation. It was revealed that there was significant difference in the occupational aspirations of students with disabilities in

integrated secondary schools. This implies that students with disabilities have different occupational aspirations. The probable reason for this finding might be due to the peculiarity attached to each disability. This finding is in consonance with the findings of Lazarus and Ihuoma (2011), Osakinle (2010) and Rufai (2004) who concluded that occupational aspirations of students with disabilities differs.

The study revealed that there was no significant sex difference in occupational aspirations of integrated secondary school students with disabilities. This implies that the occupational aspirations of male and female students with disabilities are at equal level. This finding however contradicted the submission of Groce (2007), who found gender difference in favour of male students.

The study also revealed that religion did not significantly differentiate the occupational aspirations of integrated secondary school students with disabilities. This implies that students with disabilities irrespective of their religion have the same occupational inspiration.

Conclusion

Sequel to the findings of this study, it was concluded that students with disabilities have highest preference for business based occupation, closely followed by art/humanity based occupation and science based occupation while the least preference was technology based occupation. It was also concluded that the occupational aspirations of students with disabilities in integrated secondary schools differ. In addition, occupational aspirations of integrated secondary school students with disabilities do not differ based on their gender and religion.

Recommendations

Based on the findings of this study, the following recommendations were made.

1. Parents should only guide their children in their occupational decision and not insisting on taking up occupations that will please them
2. The government should create a department that will provide career guidance for students with disabilities

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